

SARAYMULKHANIM AS A CREATIVE PERSON

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Annotation. This article will talk about the activities of the temuri Princess Saroymulkhanim in political, social and cultural life, creative work and the work done in the way of the country's prosperity.

Keywords. Saraymulkhanim, Princess, patronage activities, architecture, literature, art.

Introduction. With the princes of Temur and temurids, a number of princesses from the temurids Dynasty also grew up from talented politics, mature sukhandon and world-famous scholars. We know that in all of most states, a ruler stands on top of the state. In the management of the state, the consorts of these rulers also have an invisible power. We can also see in the construction industry what the princesses did during the Timurid era. As we make sheets of history reporting from Kohna Mozi, we witness that in all areas of the social sphere, along with men, the names of the owners of great courage have been glorified. Women also grew up with ambitious rulers, wise men, mature sages, great scholars, and ingenious art critics. Women also have a role in public administration during the Timurid di. The role of Queens in the construction of many architectural monuments and madrasas during this period is great.

Even in the Timurid period, the importance of princesses in construction work was very great. We can see many interesting manuscripts and stone works about the temurian princesses about them. II. Literature analysis and methods. We can know from works such as Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's "Zaraftara", Nizamiddin Shomi's "Zafartama", Ibn Arabshah's "wonders of fate in the news of Temur". Such works also cite the role, importance, and creative work of the malikla in state affairs. When we talk about the temurian princesses, we can see the creative work that initially made my wife Saraymulkhanim, the wife of the Noble Emir Timur. Even the fact that Saraymulkhanim sponsored my construction work comes in the jewels of history. Saraymulkhanim asks Amir Temur for permission to build a madrasa. When Amir Temur agrees his father buys a Kazakh-gifted and spends this money on Saraymulkhanim madrasah. Under the Timurids, Queens of high quality their wise advice in public administration was also taken into account. Under the Timurids, the deeds performed by the princesses were highly valued.

It is known from this that in the Timurid period, the emphasis on the Mali was strong. Amir Temur, who marched to India in 1398, intends, according to historians of the time, "if I return to Samarkand unharmed, I will build the jome mosque". Having conducted successful military campaigns on Indian soil, Amir Temur defeated the Delhi Sultanate and returned to Samarkand in the spring of 1399. A caravan of 95 elephants, many horses, camels and many other booty enters Samarkand on 29 April 1399. Amir Temur then decrees the construction of

a new jome mosque opposite the Madrasa of Bibihonim in early may 1399 to fulfill his intention. On the fourth day of Ramadan (19 May 1399 CE), the construction work of the mosque begins. Repairs will continue day and night.

After all, Amir Temur jome had intended to complete the construction of the mosque before the march towards China. In November 1404, as a result of heavy snowfall and severe frosts, construction work was halted. But before that, the main work was almost complete. After the death of Emir Temür in February 1405, the mosque will not be rebuilt. Although the monument was built by Amir Temur, it is more popularly referred to as Bibihonim jome mosque. Bibikhonim was the daughter of Emir Kazan of the House of Chigatoy, who ruled Central Asia in the 40s of the 14th century. Who name was Saroymulksanim, and she married Amir Temur in 1370. There are several different views on the naming of the mosque. One of them states that the construction of the mosque was not yet completed at the time when Amir Temur was on his way to the west March (1399). After going for a walk, the construction of the mosque was led by Bibikhonim, who From 1895 to 1896, professor N.Under veselovsky's leadership, P.Pokrishkin, artist and photographer S.Dudin, photographer I.Chistyakov, architect-artist N.Shyerbina-Kramarenko, A.With the participation of Shusev and others, a historical and architectural expedition to Samarkand is organized.

As part of the expedition, Amir Temur jome mosque was built by architect-artist N.Being researched by Shyerbina-Kramarenko, it is scientifically substantiated that this building is actually a jome mosque built by Amir Temur, not a bibhonim madrasa. After that, the building begins to be named as a mosque again. The name bibikhonim, however, remains, and many still refer to this Mahabat Mosque of Sahibqiran as "Bibikhonim jome mosque".

Conclusion. few months later, however, Amir Temur is forced to draw an army to the West because of the situation that has arisen. Amir Temur's March would last for nearly five years. Even at this time, the construction of the mosque did not stop and was almost completed in the summer months of 1404.

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